

Fluorographene-derived colloidal dispersions for donepezil delivery: From chemical synthesis to engineering of drug carriers

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Controllable synthesis of fluorographene-derived materials.
- Colloidal behavior of graphene acid derivatives.
- High biocompatibility.
- Donepezil high loading efficiency in graphene colloidal dispersion.
- Investigation of the interactions between graphene-based carriers and donepezil.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Fluorinated graphene oxide (FGO) colloidal dispersions have recently emerged as promising drug delivery systems. In this study, graphene acid (GA) and its partially fluorinated counterpart (FGA) were synthesized and

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Donepezil
Biocompatibility
Drug loading

characterized comprehensively. Both GA and FGA formed stable colloidal dispersions in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, 1 mg/mL) after sonication, with particle size and surface charge strongly influenced by surface chemistry and interparticle interactions. Biocompatibility tests indicated that neither GA nor FGA exhibits cytotoxicity, as high cell viability remained across all tested concentrations. Donepezil (Don) was chosen as a model Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API) in order to evaluate the drug-loading capacity of FGA. Simple mixing of FGA with Don resulted in efficient drug loading, while molecular dynamic and quantum-chemical studies provided molecular-level insight into FGA-donepezil interactions. Overall, these findings demonstrate that FGA is a biocompatible nanocarrier with potential added value for pharmaceutical applications.

1. Introduction

Since the isolation and study of graphene in 2004 [1], graphene-based materials have been widely employed in various biomedical applications [2–5]. Owing to its exceptional properties, such as large surface area, chemical stability, and biocompatibility, along with the ability to permeate cell membranes, graphene is considered an ideal carrier for the development of novel and advanced drug delivery systems (DDSs) [6,7]. However, the wide application of pristine graphene in nanomedicine is limited due to its extremely low dispersibility in aqueous media. Chemical modification of graphene has been launched as an effective approach to overcome the aforementioned hurdle, even leading to the preparation of graphene derivatives with high water dispersion [8]. In particular, graphene oxide (GO), as the commonest hydrophilic graphene derivative [9], has been extensively applied as a graphene-based platform in DDSs [10–12]. In this frame, bioactive molecules are loaded onto GO either covalently, via the formation of chemical bonds with the numerous oxygen moieties of GO, or non-covalently, by adsorption onto the surface of GO [10]. However, the harsh oxidation conditions applied for the synthesis of GO affect its structure, as they result in the formation of an ill-defined nanostructure bearing randomly distributed various oxygen units over the graphene lattice. Hence, the complex structure and the non-controllable synthesis of GO restrict its reproducibility [13], whereas contradictory findings can be extracted by similar studies [14]. Consequently, there is a need for the development of well-defined graphene derivatives as vehicles in DDSs.

In recent years, the chemistry of fluorographene (FG) has been widely applied as an effective strategy for the preparation of tunable and well-defined graphene derivatives [15–19]. In this context, FG-derived materials have been effectively employed in bio-applications [20–23]. As a fully fluorinated graphene analogue, FG exhibits the inherent characteristics of graphene (i.e., high chemical and thermal stability, biocompatibility, hydrophobicity, and large surface area), along with unique electronic and optical properties, owing to the presence of C-F bonds [15,19]. However, the superhydrophobic nature of FG, like graphene, restricts its potential use in biomedical applications. In order to overcome this obstacle, the treatment of fluorinated graphite (GrF), a commercially available precursor for obtaining FG via exfoliation) with strong acids is applied as the simplest approach for the preparation of water dispersible fluorinated graphene derivatives [i.e., fluorinated GO (FGO) materials], which are considered as alternative and/or advanced GO derivatives [24–27]. According to the synthetic mechanism, a

significant amount of fluorine atoms on the skeleton of FG is sacrificed during the oxidation process, resulting in the introduction of oxygen moieties and the formation of aromatic regions on the carbon lattice of FG. Such nanomaterials have been effectively employed as contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) [24] or drug delivery platforms [27], which exhibit enhanced photothermal performance, in parallel [24–26]. Notably, theoretical calculations demonstrated that the presence of fluorine atoms in FGO offers more active sites for intermolecular interactions between the nanomaterial and loading drug, compared to GO [26]. As the synthesis of fluorinated graphene derivatives with hydrophilic character (e.g., FGO) faces challenges due to the performance of non-controllable processes, like the synthesis of GO, FG-derived materials prepared under controllable conditions could be used as alternative nanocarriers in DDSs. Towards this end, recently, a comprehensive safety assessment of cyanographene (GCN) and graphene acid (GA), prominent members among FG-derived materials, demonstrated them as potential candidates in nanomedicine [28].

Donepezil is an acetylcholine esterase (AChE) inhibitor, used primarily for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease [29]. According to the working mechanism, donepezil increases the level of acetylcholine in the brain, due to AChE inhibition, thus improving cognitive function in patients [30]. However, its oral administration as a free drug faces major problems. For instance, donepezil exhibits limited penetration into the brain, with cerebrospinal fluid concentration being significantly lower compared to plasma levels [31]. Hence, its permeability through the blood-brain barrier (BBB) is not completely effective, thus reducing its therapeutic effect and limiting the amount of drug that reaches the neurons [32]. Additionally, donepezil is primarily metabolized in the liver, with metabolites showing lower brain permeability, which can affect the brain levels and, by extension, its brain bioavailability, leading to fluctuations in dosage [33,34]. The loading of donepezil on materials playing the role of nanocarriers has been applied as an elegant approach to solve its administration problem [29]. Towards this end, graphene quantum dots and MoS₂ have been employed [35,36] as representative examples of carbon-based and two-dimensional nanomaterials, respectively. Therefore, the development of novel and well-defined graphene derivatives as platforms for delivering donepezil in DDSs is a very interesting concept for study.

In this work, we report on the study of FG-derived nanomaterials, GA, and partially fluorinated GA (i.e., FGA), as drug delivery platforms. The aforementioned nanomaterials were synthesized by applying the well-established FG chemistry. Notably, a graphene derivative (i.e., FGA) was employed as carrier for delivering donepezil for the first time.

Scheme 1. Illustration of the synthesis of GA and FGA.

Fig. 1. Characterization of FGA: (a) FT-IR spectra of graphene derivatives FG, FGA, and GA, (b) survey XPS spectra of FG, FGA, and GA, (c) composition of FG, FGA, and GA based on the XPS analysis, (d) deconvoluted C 1s HR-XPS spectra of FGA and GA, (e) Raman spectra of FG, FGA, and GA, and (f) thermogravimetric analysis of FG, FGA, and GA.

Physicochemical characteristics, biological studies, and theoretical calculations demonstrated the effectiveness of FGA as a platform for donepezil. For this reason, this study could be a road map for the scientists working in the field of colloids for pharmaceutical applications, since preformulation, formulation, and biological evaluation of the systems align a full picture of the material's behavior.

2. Results and discussion

FG layers were obtained via liquid-phase exfoliation from bulk GrF, using isopropanol as the exfoliated agent [37]. Concerning the synthesis of GA and partially fluorinated GA (FGA), well-established protocols were followed (Scheme 1) [16,38]. Briefly, cyano groups attacked the electrophilic carbons of FG via a nucleophilic substitution mechanism (S_N), displacing fluorine atoms and promoting the concurrent heterolytic cleavage of the C-F bonds. Using the proper amount of cyano precursor (i.e., pseudohalide units act as nucleophiles), "fluorine-free" cyanographene (GCN) and partially fluorinated cyanographene (FGCN)

were synthesized. Afterwards, acidic hydrolysis of the cyano groups resulted in the formation of the corresponding GA and FGA, respectively. Both materials, GA and FGA, were obtained in powder after extensive washing with several solvents and centrifugations, dialysis, and freeze-drying.

Concerning their characterization, Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy was employed to identify the attached functional groups on the lattice of graphene-based materials (Scheme 1). The FT-IR spectrum of FGA displayed the characteristic sharp peak of C-F bonds at 1200 cm⁻¹, which was absent from the FT-IR spectrum of GA (Fig. 1a). Additionally, the bands of the C=O group of carboxylic acids and C=C of the graphene network for both GA and FGA appeared in the range of 1725 and 1580 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 1a), respectively. Additional bands of collective vibrations of carboxyl groups were evident in the FT-IR spectrum of GA.

Atomic content analyses of FG and its graphene derivatives (i.e., GA and FGA) were obtained by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). According to their survey spectra (Fig. 1b), the F/C atomic ratios were

Table 1

The physicochemical characteristics of the samples.

Sample	Z-Average (nm)	PDI	Zeta Potential (mV)
FG	1319	0.671	-42.2 ± 6.6
FGA	1925	0.817	-14.2
GA	1546	0.849	18.3
FGA_Don	485	0.423	-28.6

found to be 1.28 and 0.14 for FG and FGA, respectively, verifying the existence of residual fluorine atoms in FGA. In parallel, the XPS data revealed the “fluorine-free” structure of GA. Regarding the C/O atomic ratios of FGA and GA, the recorded values (i.e., 5.2 and 3.8 for GA and FGA, respectively) indicated the introduction of a higher number of oxygenated moieties (i.e., carboxyl groups) on the surface of GA with respect to FGA (Fig. 1c). In this context, the high-resolution C 1s XPS spectrum of FGA corroborated the presence of a C-F component at 289.3 eV, whereas its comparison with the corresponding spectrum of GA concerning the intensities of the O=C–O component, located at 288.8 eV, indicated the higher loading of GA by COOH groups with respect to FGA (Fig. 1d).

Raman spectroscopy also provided significant structural information for FG, GA, and FGA (Fig. 1e). Whereas the fully fluorinated precursor FG is a Raman silent material [39], the Raman spectra of GA and FGA displayed the characteristic D and G bands at around 1345 and 1595 cm^{-1} , ascribed to the sp^3 hybridized carbon atoms and to the sp^2 ones, respectively. The ratios of I_D and I_G band intensities for GA and FGA were found to be 0.94 and 0.90, respectively, thus indicating a higher number of defects in the lattice of GA in comparison to FGA.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) provided significant insight into the thermal stability of graphene derivatives. In the current study, the thermal stabilities of FG, FGA, and GA were evaluated by measuring them under a nitrogen atmosphere. FG is thermally stable up to 400 °C, and its decomposition occurs between 450 and 640 °C, losing 75 % of its mass [40]. Decomposition of GA started at 160–600 °C, losing 24 % of its mass. Concerning the thermal stability of FGA, an initial weight loss (~2 %) at a temperature below 160 °C was attributed to the loss of adsorbed moisture. The main decomposition stage occurred at the range 160–600 °C, where FGA lost 42 % of its mass (Fig. 1f). Based on the TGA curve of FGA, a two-step weight loss process was observed, where the first decomposition (occurred between 160 and 420 °C) is associated with the loss of oxygen moieties (mainly carboxyl groups), whereas the second one (occurred between 420 and 600 °C) is ascribed to the loss of

C-F bonds, as a similar steep decline was observed in the thermal decomposition of FG.

Dynamic and electrophoretic light scattering (DLS–ELS) was employed to characterize the flake size, size distribution (polydispersity index-PDI), and zeta potential of FG, FGA, and GA (Table 1). Each material sample was prepared at a concentration of 1 mg/mL in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), and subsequently, each mixture was sonicated for 30 min to ensure homogeneity. The FGA dispersion was further diluted to one-tenth of the original concentration, while the GA solution was diluted to one-eighteenth of the original concentration. The DLS analysis revealed that FGA exhibited the highest Z-average value among the three samples, indicating that the average flake size in the FGA sample is larger compared to that of FG and GA. This result suggests that the FGA layers tend to aggregate or are inherently larger, possibly due to the interaction between their addends. In terms of PDI, the sample of FG showed the lowest value, signifying a more uniform particle size distribution within the sample. This homogeneity indicates that FG particles are relatively monodisperse. In contrast, GA demonstrated the highest PDI value, implying a broad size distribution and greater heterogeneity among the particles. The high PDI value suggests the presence of layers of varying sizes, which may be due to differences in aggregation behavior or intrinsic layer size variation. The zeta potential analysis showed that FG displayed the highest zeta potential among the aforementioned three samples. A high zeta potential indicates that FG flakes have a stronger surface charge, which enhances their electrostatic repulsion and contributes to better formulation stability in the dispersion state. In comparison, FGA and GA exhibited lower zeta potential values, indicating a reduced tendency to remain dispersed. This could lead to aggregation over time, affecting stability.

The morphologies of graphene derivatives were examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The images presented in Fig. 2 revealed the 2D structure of graphene derivatives, which consist of a few graphene layers. The morphology of the graphene derivatives is more or less the same for the three samples and those observed in the recent literature. The porosity of the GA sample is higher in comparison to the other two derivatives. There is a difference in the size of the samples' structures between the DLS and SEM measurements. We should take into account that in DLS, the size is strongly associated with the dispersion properties of the materials because of the aqueous solvent, as well as PBS ions bound around the particle. DLS measures the apparent size of the particulate systems through the Brownian motion in the solvent state. For this reason, the size of the graphene derivatives is higher in

Fig. 2. SEM images of FG, FGA, and GA.

Fig. 3. (a, b) MTT cell viability assay after 24 h treatment of HEK-293 of GA and FGA. Cell viability is expressed as % cell viability SD between two experiments. (c) Release profiles through the membrane of dialysis sack for free Don and FGA_Don formulation (mean \pm SE, $n = 3$).

comparison to the size observed by SEM images, where the particle is under high vacuum without hydration layers (Fig. 2 and Table 1). In the dispersion state, graphene derivatives tend to interact with their neighboring particles and aggregate or flocculate, whereas particles with a higher size are prepared. These differences in size and size distribution measured by DLS and SEM are widely observed in colloidal dispersions in the literature [41,42]. Additionally, taking into account the potential utilization of FGA as a drug delivery platform, the stability assessment of the FGA colloidal dispersion was evaluated. Thus, the FGA colloidal dispersion was stored at 4 °C for one month. The size, size distribution, and zeta potential were evaluated every 10 days (Table S1). Before each measurement, the vial was shaken slightly three times. The physicochemical characteristics of the FGA colloidal dispersion remained stable during the time period of the stability assessment. The size and size distribution were slightly increased at 20 days. The surface net charge of the FGA is responsible for keeping the particles in a dispersion state, avoiding the formation of flocculates or aggregates that cannot redisperse into aqueous media.

After the characterization of GA and FGA, the cytotoxicity of both graphene derivatives was studied. The main reason for the experimental procedure is to ensure that both nanomaterials are safe for pharmaceutical and biomedical applications. According to guidelines applied in pharmaceutical development, all the excipients should be safe to be used as drug delivery systems. The results indicated that neither GA nor FGA exhibits cytotoxicity, as cell viability remains high at all tested concentrations (Fig. 3a, b). In particular, FGA demonstrated a significant and unexpected increase in cell viability with increasing concentrations, suggesting a possible proliferative effect (Fig. 3b). This phenomenon may be attributed to experimental conditions, cellular responses to FGA, or procedural factors that warrant further investigation. It is well-established that GO, reduced GO, and few-layer graphene can scavenge hydroxyl radical ($\bullet\text{OH}$) [43]. Based on the literature, it was recently reported that graphene derivatives with a high number of vacancies and oxygen-containing functional groups exhibited the highest

activity in 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazil (DPPH) trapping, meaning antioxidant activity [44]. Additionally, in the same context, functionalization of GO with benzoic acid showed reaction with hydroxyl radicals [45]. The last observations from the literature, in which the functionalization is responsible for the antioxidant activity of graphene derivatives, could be a possible explanation for the unexpected increase in cell viability by FGA.

As FGA not only maintains cell viability but also enhances it at specific concentrations, FGA stands out as a promising candidate for further studies. Its ability to support or even promote cell growth makes FGA particularly suitable for progress in drug loading experiments, where maintaining cell integrity is crucial for therapeutic applications. In this frame, donepezil hydrochloride was mixed with FGA towards the preparation of the drug delivery system FGA_Donepezil (FGA_Don). The FGA_Don formulations (2:1 wt ratio, 1 mg/mL) were stirred for 2 h. Measurements showed significant differences between FGA and FGA_Don, highlighting the positive impact of drug loading on formulation properties (Table 1). The reduced Z-Average in FGA_Don suggests the development of smaller and more stable particles, due to strong FGA-Donepezil interactions, which prevent the aggregation of FGA flakes. The significant decrease in PDI after drug loading means that the system FGA_Don is mainly monodistributed and stable. Notably, the lower PDI indicates good quality of nanostructures with uniform size, which enhances the suitability of FGA as a drug delivery system. The increase in negative charge after loading donepezil is particularly positive, as a more negative zeta potential indicates better colloidal dispersion stability due to increased electrostatic repulsions. This means that the FGA_Don system is more stable and less likely to form aggregates over time. Additionally, the interactions between FGA and Don were verified through the performance of photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy. The PL emission spectrum of Don displays a dominant peak at 474 nm and weaker emission at 394 nm (Fig. S1). Upon mixing with FGA, the PL intensity of Don decreased by more than an order of magnitude (Fig. S1), indicating efficient quenching and suggesting strong interaction or

Fig. 4. (a) Time evolution of the number of adsorbed donepezil molecules on FGA (left panels), and GA (right panels). (b) Representative snapshot showing donepezil adsorption patterns with FGA/GA flakes within the simulation box. Solvent molecules are omitted for clarity. Donepezil molecules are shown in pink.

energy transfer between FGA and Don. Overall, donepezil loading enhances FGA's physicochemical properties, making it a more stable, homogeneous, and promising carrier for targeted drug delivery, improving drug stability and bioavailability.

The FGA_Don samples were prepared at a concentration of 1 mg/mL, with their volumes precisely measured. Based on this theoretical concentration, the expected drug loading was calculated. The HPLC results provided the actual donepezil concentration in the carrier, allowing for the determination of drug encapsulation. The analysis confirmed that a substantial amount of donepezil was successfully incorporated into the FGA particles, demonstrating the material's efficiency as a nanocarrier. On average, donepezil loading onto FGA was estimated at 62 %, highlighting its high drug retention capacity. This high loading capacity, combined with the observed enhancements in dispersion stability and monodispersity upon drug incorporation, indicates that FGA not only serves as a robust host material but may also protect the drug from first-pass metabolism [46] and facilitate more efficient transport across biological barriers, such as the BBB.

The release profiles of Don from the FGA_Don formulation and the corresponding free drug solution are presented in Fig. 3c. Both samples exhibited a linear release profile across the dialysis membrane, confirming the maintenance of sink conditions. By 240 min, FGA_Don and free donepezil achieved mean cumulative releases of 96.8 ± 9.81 and 95.4 ± 10.0 % of the loading doses, respectively. Free donepezil displayed a slightly faster initial permeation (burst release) during the first 60–90 min, consistent with its unrestricted diffusion in PBS. In contrast, FGA_Don showed a modestly delayed but steady release, which is indicative of transient interactions between donepezil and the FGA

flakes that slow early diffusion without hindering overall release. After 120 min, the profiles of the two systems converged, and by 240 min, both achieved comparable cumulative release levels. These findings suggest that the drug is effectively released from the FGA carrier without significant retention or prolonged entrapment, while the initial lag phase is in line with the expected desorption of donepezil from the FGA surface. Overall, the release behavior is considered consistent with the proposed FGA–drug interaction mechanisms and confirms that FGA enables complete donepezil release under the pH conditions of 7.4.

To rationalize the above-mentioned findings related to donepezil affinity with FGA, theoretical calculations were performed. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations revealed a stronger affinity of donepezil for FGA, with ~ 51 % of molecules adsorbed on its surface compared to ~ 33 % on GA (Fig. 4a), which is in line with the previous reports for fluorinated graphene derivatives [26]. Adsorption occurred preferentially at the flake edges, where donepezil frequently acted as a bridging agent between neighboring flakes (Fig. 4b). Aggregation of donepezil molecules (forming self-assembled higher-order aggregates), mainly stabilized through stacking of their indanone ends, was also observed. Additional quantitative analyses of binding geometries and flake-flake interactions are provided in the Supporting Information.

Building on the docking-derived poses of donepezil on graphene derivatives, the semiempirical PM6-DH2 screening offered a comprehensive overview of binding across multiple dissociation states and conformers (Table S2). Overall, FGA consistently showed more negative interaction energies than GA, in agreement with the higher adsorption tendency observed in MD simulations. The most stable complexes were observed for flakes with four dissociated carboxyl groups, suggesting

Table 2

Interaction energies (kcal mol⁻¹) of selected donepezil-flake complexes optimized at the B3LYP/def2-SVP level and refined by higher-level single-point calculations (B3LYP/def2-TZVP and M06-2X/def2-TZVP) in implicit water (CPCM/SMD, $\epsilon = 78.4$).

	FGA (edges)			FGA (edges+plane)			GA		
	B3LYP/def2-SVP	B3LYP/def2-TZVP	M06-2X/def2-TZVP	B3LYP/def2-SVP	B3LYP/def2-TZVP	M06-2X/def2-TZVP	B3LYP/def2-SVP	B3LYP/def2-TZVP	M06-2X/def2-TZVP
4AB	-78.2	-58.0	-57.5	-78.0	-57.6	-57.1	-75.7	-56.1	-56.0
4BB	-79.6	-57.7	-56.2	-78.0	-56.2	-53.8	-77.3	-56.1	-55.4
4GC	-85.2	-61.5	-58.4	-80.6	-59.7	-57.0	-82.9	-59.1	-57.1

that partial deprotonation provides an optimal balance between electrostatic stabilization and π - π interactions. Interaction energies for representative complexes reached ~ -40 to -65 kcal mol⁻¹, with several poses stabilized by indanone-graphene π -stacking.

To gain a more accurate description of binding, we refined at the density functional theory (DFT) level the three most stable complexes with four dissociated carboxyl groups (4AB, 4BB and 4GC; the poses and naming convention are explained in the footnote of Table S2 and illustrated in Fig. S2). Geometry optimization at B3LYP/def2-SVP followed by higher-level single-point corrections showed that FGA was consistently slightly more stabilizing than GA. At the M06-2X/def2-TZVP level, the interaction energies were -57.5 kcal mol⁻¹ for 4AB/FGA vs. -56.0 kcal mol⁻¹ for 4AB/GA, -56.2 kcal mol⁻¹ for 4BB/FGA vs. -55.4 kcal mol⁻¹ for 4BB/GA, and -58.4 kcal mol⁻¹ for 4GC/FGA vs. -57.1 kcal mol⁻¹ for 4GC/GA (Table 2). Although the absolute differences were modest (≈ 0.8 – 1.5 kcal mol⁻¹), they consistently indicated an additional stabilizing contribution from fluorine substituents, supporting the experimental expectation that FGA has a higher adsorption affinity than GA.

The consistency between MD simulations (indicating a higher average number of adsorbed molecules on FGA) and DFT calculations (showing more favorable interaction energies for FGA) underscores the robustness of this conclusion across different methods and system sizes. Overall, the results suggest that fluorine substituents subtly enhance donepezil adsorption, while partial deprotonation of the flake (4 COOH groups, i.e., ~ 30 % deprotonation) provides the most favorable balance of stabilization.

3. Conclusions

We synthesized a biocompatible and non-toxic partially fluorinated graphene derivative under mild and controllable conditions. Physicochemical studies of the colloidal dispersions revealed self-assembly into particles of 1300–2000 nm, with surface chemistry influencing both size distribution and zeta potential. Moreover, biocompatibility assays confirmed the safety of colloidal dispersions over a wide concentration range, which is a fundamental prerequisite for their pharmaceutical application as drug delivery systems. Within this framework, FGA was successfully applied for the encapsulation of donepezil, achieving a drug loading efficiency of ~ 62 %, consistent with theoretical simulations. DFT calculations further indicated that fluorination enhances donepezil adsorption relative to non-fluorinated GA. Importantly, an extra advantage of the utilization of FGA as a carrier is that a significantly lower amount of NaCN was employed for its synthesis compared to that used for GA, which reflects lower production of hazardous cyanide byproducts during the process, whereas the presence of fluorine atoms enhances donepezil adsorption. In conclusion, this investigation highlights FGA as a viable multifunctional excipient for the design and development of pharmaceutical dosage and establishes a procedure for assessing recently synthesized graphene derivatives, including physicochemical, morphological, thermodynamic, solution behavior, and stability assessment.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Themistoklis Aivaliotis: Investigation, Formal analysis. **Nefeli Lagopati:** Validation, Investigation. **Pavlos Pantelis:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Evangelia A. Pavlatou:** Validation, Formal analysis. **Maria-Anna Gatou:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Vítězslav Hrubý:** Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Paraskevi Papakyriakopoulou:** Writing – original draft, Validation. **Vassilis G. Gorgoulis:** Validation, Data curation. **Natassa Pippa:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Demetrios D. Chronopoulos:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Sergii Kalytchuk:** Data curation, Formal analysis. **Sofia-Anna Ntousi:** Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Martin Pykal:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.colsurfa.2025.139225](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2025.139225).

Data Availability

Data on the characterization of graphene materials plotted in this study, and theoretical calculations are available via Zenodo repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17867497>. The rest data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon request.

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